

ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF HISTORICAL LAND USE AND LAND COVER CHANGES ON ECOSYSTEM SERVICES: EVIDENCE FROM SARGODHA, PUNJAB, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Ecosystems' diverse patterns, characteristics, and functions are crucial in achieving sustainable development. Land use and land cover changes (LULCCs) substantially affect ecosystems that provide essential services and are expected to increase degradation in the 21st century. Therefore, this study explores changes in ecosystem service values (ESVs) in response to LULCCs and the historical changes (2000–2023) in Sargodha district, Pakistan. Costanza's valuation coefficients, Landsat-8 OLI imagery, and the benefit transfer method were utilized. Land use changes significantly impact greenhouse gas emissions, water budgets, and the carbon cycle. The study revealed that the cropland increased by 2.28%, but built-up areas increased significantly by 12.29%. The ESVs increased from 3,056.39 million US dollars in 2000 to 3,304 million US dollars in 2023, but ecosystem services were negatively impacted by a 12.53% decrease in natural vegetation. Urbanization was the primary driver of the most significant increase (58.90%) in recreational ESVs. Reduced natural vegetation led to a drop in cultural, habitat, and gas control, while other services, such as climate regulation, experienced growth. Ecosystems are seriously threatened by LULC changes, such as deforestation, driven by the growing global population. So, it is becoming an increasingly important component of land use planning due to the need to balance environmental and human concerns. Policies that ensure sustainable ecosystem services in the face of changing land use, particularly in establishing forest land conservation systems.

INTRODUCTION

Ecosystem services (ES)—benefits derived from the structure, function, and composition of ecosystems—are vital to the sustainable development goals. Ecosystems are very vital for Earth as they set up and maintain a human life-support system (Nelson et al., 2009) The terrestrial ecosystem, the most proximate

human ecosystem, provides pervasive ecosystem services, such as freshwater, soil, and biological resources. Furthermore, it serves as the physical basis and material security of the human civilization development.

As a major global change driver, land use and land cover changes (LULCCs) directly affect the health and integrity of ecosystems and can dramatically alter their capacity to provide ecosystem services in the long term. As shown in few recent studies, land use change is becoming better seen as fundamentally related to the provision of ecosystem services (Bryan et al., 2018; Karimifard and Moghaddam, 2018; Schröter et al., 2019). An increase in urbanization over the past decades, for instance, carries a serious resource consumption, fragmentation and loss of biodiversity, which comes as a negative consequence of LULC changes (Butler et al., 2013). The grassland expansion fundamentally changed the structure and functions of the landscape and decreased the supply of ES due to LULC change. However, and these include the production of new landscape elements (such as roads, live fences), or a transformation in a site's capacity to deliver ES (reduce, detract, unchanged or enhance) (Habib et al., 2016). Nevertheless, LULC decisions have preserved ecological resources and ecosystem services and have the capacity to aid in social and economic benefit, via the adoption of conservation strategies, such as the establishment of protected sites (Abram et al., 2014). And hence, LULCCs affect traits of habitat associated with biodiversity as well as ecosystem services important for the sustainability of human life. Land management can involve compromises or trade-offs where some methods can improve the provision of some ecosystem services at the expense of others (Quintas-Soriano et al., 2016). Understanding how land use/land cover (LULC) changes determine the provision of ecosystem services (ES) is key to identify opportunities to enhance ecological restoration efforts at the landscape scale.

On a more global scale, the global concerns on land use and land cover change (LULCC) are very much known. Climate, soil quality, global biodiversity, and the ecological life support systems that meet human needs (Sagan et al., 1979, Trimble and Crosson, 2000, Sala et al., 2000, Vitousek et al., 1997) are jeopardized. Land use change must then be comprehended for effective environmental management because land is the basis of the carbon cycle, greenhouse gas emissions, radiation and water budgets, and livelihoods (Turner, 1994). In this vein, land use planning and management seeks to define

land use patterns that will emerge through land use changes while at the same time trying to find a balance among the different interests of multiple stakeholders and environmental requirements (Verburg et al., 2002).

At present about 60% of ESs are declining or being used unsustainable (Assessment-MEA, 2005) and this type of deterioration is predicted to rise markedly in the first 50 years of the 21st century (Vihervaara et al. In recent years, due to their ability to track and communicate relationships between human-beings and the environment, an increasing number of ES studies have been performed jointly with ecosystem degradation and change [10,11]. Ecosystem services are not uniform or stable through time and space; they are often characterized by spatial heterogeneity (Fisher et al 2009; Barbier, 2012; Akhtar et al 2021). Today, 40% of the land area of the planet is used for farming or grazing (Foley et al., 2005), and about 13 million hectares of new agricultural area are established annually, often by clearing forests (Foley et al., 2005). LULCCs have had a significant effect on ecosystems, especially on the biotic diversity. Consequently, these changes have reduced the capacity of ecosystems to continuously deliver the goods and services society needs for the survival of its present and future generations [7, 8]. (Metzger et al., 2006; Balvanera et al., 2006; Mendoza-González et al., 2012). Conversion of the natural habitat into croplands, tree habitations and different non-rural suburban areas has led to a huge growth of the worldwide manufacture of food, fiber, timber, housing and other goods. These changes in land use and land cover (LULCC) are linked with other global processes, like population growth, land degradation, and global climate change. Climate change is closely associated with land use change. According to (Foley et al., 2005), approximately 35% of all human CO₂ emissions are already caused by land use directly since 1850. It is widely accepted that although population growth is unevenly distributed around the world and is followed by an accelerating human footprint, the sensible use of land is not changed accordingly (Szabó et al., 2016). There is no denying that land cover change, in the form of deforestation, does significant damage to the earth's ecosystems and land (Foley et al., 2005; Lawler et al., 2014).

Land monitoring and assessment is an essential part of global change research, and has been for at least twenty years (Lambin et al. 2001; Jung et al. Since vegetation is the foundation of life and plays an important role in climate change, it is highly necessary to classify and map vegetation to support the management of natural resources (Xiao et al., 2004). Remote sensing images are analyzed using interpretation components and association data to become vegetation information. Before carrying out the extraction of vegetation, pre-processing of satellite images is required to reduce noise (Schowengerdt, 2006) and to increase the intelligibility of the image data (Campbell and Wynne, 2011). Image pre-processing can be tailored depending on the features sought but usually includes multiple procedures (Hall et al., 1991), the aim of picture pre-processing is to normalize all images so they look as if they were taken by the same sensor, though is likely different sensors have been used. These processes include replacing bad lines, radiometric correction, geometric correction, image enhancement and masking. All these pre-processing steps contribute to normalization and enhance the uniformity of images.

In recognition of the support that LULCC provide to conservation (Balmford et al., 2002; Turner et al., 2003; Alarcon et al., 2016), the integration of ES value into land use policy is growing. An increasing variety of approaches to valuing ES are being developed alongside assessments of land use change. The study from Costanza et al. Land use-based value of ES (1997) Inspired by this study, numerous efforts have been initiated to quantify changes in ES and associated values due to land-use change assessments (e.g., Kreuter et al., 2001; Zhao et al., 2004; Polasky et al., 2011; Mendoza-González et al., 2012; Talberth, 2015; Wang et al., 2015; Tolessa et al., 2017; Yee et al., 2021). This is what many studies have done. Currently, the valuation of ES is limited to some services (Polasky et al., 2011; Viglizzo et al., 2012; Boithias et al., 2016; Hamel and Bryant, 2017), and these global measurements are not exhaustive. Still, the cloud of uncertainty related to ES valuation quantification has been somewhat alleviated over the years.

A growing global concern is how to reduce the negative legacy of urbanisation and economic development upon ecosystems and their services. The

services rendered by these sorts of ecosystem are public goods and is not measured full, which is quite a problem (Costanza et al., 2014; McDonald et al., 2014). Quantification and valuing of ecosystem services are essential decision-support tools for sustainable land use. This allows for a realistic analysis of land-use option trade-offs, allowing for broader analysis of impact and benefit. The first step towards characterizing the regionality of ecosystem services (ES) is their measurement. The literature describes several methods for achieving this including the benefit transfer method, cost-based methods (replacement cost and avoiding cost), revealed preference methods (travel cost and market price), and stated preference methods (choice experiments and contingent valuation). Those techniques offer the chance of performance evaluation and quantification of ST local resources wealth (Costanza et al., 1997; Talberth, 2015; Arowolo et al., 2018).

As of 2023, Sargodha is the 12th most populated city in Pakistan; however, the city is expected to grow 43.7% to 6.23 million people by 2050 (Punjab Bureau of Statistics, 2023), driving an urgent need for urban planning based on food security during localized crises. Given the pressure of the environment and forest supply of the country already at their peak due to deforestation, this increase in population will be adding on the already existing human pressure on the scarce land resource. Consequently, monitoring LULC changes and their impact on ecosystem services value (ESV) are crucial for sustainable land use and natural ecosystem management in Sargodha. Our research is done to answer two key questions:

- To explore historical land use/land cover changes from 2000 to 2023
- To evaluate the variations in ecosystem services values (ESVs) in response to actual LULCCs

Methodology

2.1. Study Area

Study area: The Sargodha district is located over Potohar plateau available in the Punjab province. It lies at an altitude of 625ft above sea level and has the following map coordinates (32°5'1" N 72°40'16" E). Sargodha lies approximately 40 km (25 mi) to the northwest of the Chenab River one of the main branches of Indus River. The study area expands of 5828 sq. The climate of Sargodha is subtropical semi-

arid, characterised by dry and mild winters (but in which the nights are often chilly), and rainy and hot summers due to the Indian monsoon km. Average temperature throughout the coldest month (January)

is of 11.9 °C (53.3 °F) while the hottest month (June) is of 33.6 °C (92.4 °F).

Fig.1. Location of study area in the map of Pakistan

2.2. Data Acquiring

In this study, we acquired satellite imageries from Landsat 7 ETM+ C2L2 for 23 December 2000 and Landsat 8 OLI_TIRS C2L2 for 22 June 2023 with less than 5% cloud cover. All the data is geometrically and atmospherically corrected with the spatial and temporal resolution of 30m and 16d, respectively. The data is downloaded in GeoTIFF format from USGS Earth Explorer (<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>) which is a well-known platform for satellite imageries, globally. The X,Y coordinate system is WGS_1984_UTM_Zone_43N for both imageries as the study area fall under this coordinate system.

2.3. LULC Change Analysis

Land use/land cover area is classified into 5 classes: Cropland, Natural Vegetation, Water-bodies, Built-up area and Unused land. We used Cropland as proxy for cultivated land; Savannas, Shrub-lands and grasslands as Natural Vegetation; Rivers as Water-bodies; Urban areas and villages as Built-up area and Bare-land and Rocks as unused land. Supervised Maximum Likelihood classification is done to classify the LULC area. For year 2000, more than 600 training samples were selected which have given 83%

overall accuracy and 0.79 Kappa coefficient of land use/land cover area and for year 2023, more than 1000 training samples were selected which results 88% overall accuracy and 0.85 Kappa coefficient. ArcGIS 10.7 is used for compiling and analyzing LULC data.

2.4. Ecosystem Services Valuation

We used Benefit Transfer Method for the valuation of ecosystem services and used the value coefficients used by (Costanza *et al.*, 1997). We selected the Costanza's valuation coefficients for ES valuation for two reasons; 1) these are the most comprehensive valuation coefficients providing 16 biome and 17 ecosystem services functions, 2) we had lack of funds for our research to conduct the field survey and developing the questionnaire in order to determine the total ESVs.

2.5. Calculation of ESVs

To calculate the ESVs we followed the Costanza's assessment model for ESVs which is also used in many other studies such as (Kreuter *et al.*, 2001; Zhao *et al.*, 2004; Li *et al.*, 2007):

$$ESV_t = \sum_{k=1}^n (A_{kt} \times VC_k)$$

where; ESV_t is the estimated total ESV at time t , A_{kt} is the area (ha) of LULC type k at time t and VC_k is the ESVs coefficient ($US\$ha^{-1} yr^{-1}$) of the LULC type k . The change in ESVs in terms of percentage is assessed by using the formula:

$$ESV_{cr} = (ESV_{t2} - ESV_{t1} / ESV_{t1}) \times 100$$

ESV_{t2} and ESV_{t1} are the calculated total ESVs at the end and the start of study period, $t2$ and $t1$, respectively. ESV_{cr} is the change in the rate of ESVs over the observation period from $t1$ to $t2$. We assessed the effects of such alterations on the various ecosystem functions in addition to assessing the effect of LULC

change on Sargodha's overall ESVs. The following equation is used to determine the value of services offered by various ecosystem functions:

$$ESV_{ft} = \sum_{k=1}^n (A_{kt} \times VC_{fk})$$

where; ESV_{ft} represents the estimated Ecosystem Service Value of function f at a specific time t , A_{kt} and VC_k correspond to the area in hectares and the coefficient of Ecosystem Service Value of function f in US dollars per hectare per year ($US\$ha^{-1} yr^{-1}$) respectively, for the specific Land Use Land Cover (LULC) type k .

Table 1

Costanza et al. (2014) ESV coefficients ($US\$ha^{-1} yr^{-1}$) of the equivalent biome for the LULC types in Sargodha division.

Service type	Sub Type	CL	NV	WB	BU	UL
Provisioning	Food Provisioning	2,323	1,192	106	0	0
	Raw Materials	219	54	0	0	0
	Gas Regulation	0	9	0	0	0
	Climate regulation	411	40	0	905	0
Regulating	Disturbance regulation	0	0	0	0	0
	Water regulation	0	3	7,514	16	0
	Water supply	400	60	1,808	0	0
	Waste treatment	397	75	918	0	0
	Erosion control	107	44	0	0	0
	Soil formation	532	2	0	0	0
	Nutrient cycling	0	0	0	0	0
Supporting	Pollination	22	35	0	0	0
	Biological control	33	31	0	0	0
	Habitat/refugia	0	1,214	0	0	0
	Genetic resources	1,042	1,214	0	0	0
Recreation and Culture	Recreation	82	26	2,166	5,740	0
	Cultural	0	167	0	0	0
Total ESV		5,568	4,166	12512	6661	0

Results

3.1. Land use land cover patterns in Sargodha

Land use analysis of the study area has showed significant change in the cropland area. It is observed that the most dominant LULC class of the study area is cropland which covered 47.75% of the total area of Sargodha in year 2000 and 50.04% in year 2023 with

increase of 2.29% from year 2000. The increase of 13295.22 hac is noticed from 278367.75 hac in year 2000 to 291662.98 hac in year 2023. This increase has been noticed mostly in the northeast and the southeast region of Sargodha. The second most dominant class is built-up area which has been

increased from 109776.14 hac, 18.83% in 2000 to 181420.71 hac 31.13% in 2023. The increment is 71644.57 hac which is 12.29% increase during the span of 23 years. Major changes in built-up area can be noticed from the northwestern, southwestern and in the middle of the region where the Sargodha city is located. Significant decline is occurred in natural vegetation which covered 22.26% of the total area in 2000 but in 2023 it reduced to just 9.72%. The decrease of 73058.39 hac can be observed from

129728.97 in 2000 to 56670.58 in 2023. The mostly change occurred in the south, east and north of the region. A slight decrease is observed in unused land which was 7.92% or 46214.07 hac in 2000 but remained 34280.31 hac in 2023 which covered the 5.88% of the total area. Waterbodies remains almost constant throughout the period from 18763.23 hac in 2000 to 18813.64 hac in 2023.

Table 2

Conversion matrix of LULC change (hac) in Sargodha from 2000 to 2023

LULC Change (hac)	2023					
	Built-up	Cropland	Natural Vegetation	Unused Land	Waterbodies	Total
Built-up	50438.92	35399.34	9923.74	9853.34	4136.12	109751.46
Cropland	67622.18	180164.80	19988.80	7110.95	3453.14	278339.86
Natural Vegetation	43994.71	61085.61	14144.02	7224.25	3258.64	129707.22
Unused Land	13245.35	9604.25	10024.00	7643.25	5677.53	46194.38
Waterbodies	6091.92	5373.67	2574.40	2435.90	2280.79	18756.68
Total	181393.07	291627.66	56654.96	34267.70	18806.21	582749.61

Fig. 2. Spatial pattern of historical LULC in study area, year 2000

Fig. 3. Spatial pattern of historical LULC in study area, year 2023

Table 3
LULC changing patterns in Sargodha from 2000 to 2023 and their comparison

LULC Class	2000		2023		2000-2023	
	Area (hac)	%	Area (hac)	%	Difference (hac)	%
Cropland	278367.75	50.04	291662.98	47.76	-13295.22	-2.28
Natural Vegetation	129728.97	9.72	56670.58	22.26	73058.39	12.53
Waterbodies	18763.23	3.23	18813.64	3.22	-50.41	-0.01
Builtup	109776.14	31.13	181420.71	18.83	-71644.57	-12.29
Unused Land	46214.07	5.88	34280.31	7.93	11933.75	2.05

Fig. 4. Comparison of historical LULC areas from year 2000-2023

3.2. ESV Estimation

Based on Costanza’s ecosystem services valuation coefficients, in 2000, the total estimated ESVs of Sargodha were 3056.39 million US\$ from which the cropland was the most dominant class providing ESVs of 1549.95 million US\$ (50.71% of total ESVs) followed by built-up area which provided 731.22 million US\$ (23.92% of ESVs), natural vegetation and waterbodies with 540.45 (17.68%) and 234.77 million US\$ (7.68% of ESVs), respectively. In year 2023, the total ESVs calculated were 3304 million US\$ and the cropland showed dominance by providing 1623.98 million US\$ of ESVs followed by built-up area with estimated ESVs of 1208.44 million US\$. Ecosystem services generated from natural vegetation are spotted to be declined to 236.09 million US\$ and ESVs from waterbodies are slightly improved and reached to 235.40 million US\$.

3.3. Changes in ESVs

We compared and quantified the overall contributions of each ecosystem functions in

Sargodha District. Increasing trends can be observed in raw materials, climate regulation, water regulation, water supply, soil formation and recreation with the rise of 99.14%, 23.53%, 0.90%, 0.67%, 4.46% and 37.07% respectively.

Cropland area provided major sum of ecosystem services functions from which the highest share comes from food provisioning which is 646.65 million US\$, or 43.41% of total ESVs generated from cropland area, followed by genetic resources which contributed 290.06 million US\$ (19.47%), soil formation with 148.09 million US\$ (9.94%), climate regulation with 114.41 million US\$ (7.68%) and water supply with 111.35 million US\$ (7.48% of cropland generated ESVs).

Food production, the primary function of ecosystem services, contributed the most ESVs in 2000, accounting for 803.27 million US dollars, or 26.87% of all ESVs. This significant amount is due to major share of cropland area in study region.

Table 4
Estimated ecosystem functions values in Sargodha in 2000-2023

Service type	Sub Type	2000		2023		2000-2023	
		10 ⁶	%	10 ⁶	%	Difference	%
Provisioning	Food Provisioning	803.27	26.28	747.08	22.61	-56.20	-3.67
	Raw Materials	67.97	2.22	66.93	2.03	-1.03	-0.20
	Gas Regulation	1.17	0.04	0.51	0.02	-0.66	-0.02
	Climate regulation	218.95	7.16	286.33	8.67	67.38	1.50
Regulating	Disturbance regulation	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Water regulation	143.13	4.68	144.44	4.37	1.31	-0.31
	Water supply	153.05	5.01	154.08	4.66	1.03	-0.34
	Waste treatment	137.47	4.50	137.31	4.16	-0.15	-0.34
	Erosion control	35.49	1.16	33.70	1.02	-1.79	-0.14
	Soil formation	148.35	4.85	155.28	4.70	6.93	-0.15
Supporting	Nutrient cycling	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Pollination	10.66	0.35	8.40	0.25	-2.26	-0.09
	Biological control	13.21	0.43	11.38	0.34	-1.83	-0.09
	Habitat/refugia	157.49	5.15	68.80	2.08	-88.69	-3.07
Recreation and Culture	Genetic resources	447.55	14.64	372.71	11.28	-74.84	-3.36
	Recreation	696.96	22.80	1107.50	33.52	410.54	10.72
	Cultural	21.66	0.71	9.46	0.29	-12.20	-0.42

Table 5
Ecosystem services value (ESV) by land use type and the change in Sargodha from 2000 to 2010

	CL	NV	WB	BU	UL	Total
ESV 2000 (10 ⁶ USD)	1,549.95	540.45	234.77	731.22	0	3,056.39
ESV 2000 (%)	50.71	17.68	7.68	23.92	0	100
ESV 2023 (10 ⁶ USD)	1,623.98	236.09	235.40	1,208.44	0	3,303.91
ESV2023 (%)	49.15	7.15	7.12	36.58	0	100
ESV Change 2000-2023 (10 ⁶ USD)	74.03	-304.36	0.63	477.22	0	247.52
ESVChange %	4.78	-56.32	0.27	65.26	0	13.99

Discussion

4.1. LULC patterns

Cropland dominated the study throughout the observation period. In 2000, the area covered by cropland was 47.76% while in 2023, this area increased up-to 50.04% with the growth of 2.28% indicating the agricultural potential in the region. This increase is mainly due to the conversion of unused land into cropland which covered 7.93% in 2000 and reduced to 5.88% with the decline of 2.05%. the second most dominant LULC class is

built-up area which covered just 18.83% of the region in 2000 and significantly raised up-to 31.13% in 2023 with the significant increase of 12.29%. The main reason of the increment of this class is the rural-urban migration due to poverty and lack of income opportunities in rural or sub-urban areas. Another reason is the population growth. According to the population census done in 1998 by Pakistan bureau of statistics (PBS) (Statistics, 1998), the population of Sargodha district was 2,665,979 which has been increased up-to 3,696,212 in year 2017 (Statistics,

2017) which has been grown up-to 72.13% and with the annual growth rate of 1.73%. A significant reduction can be observed in the LULC class named as Natural Vegetation which was covering 22.26% of the region in 2000 but in 2023, it is reduced to just 9.72% with the decline of 12.53%. The major part of natural vegetation converted into cropland which is 61085.61 hac which indicate the focus toward agriculture in the region. The other major portion of natural vegetation is converted into built-up area which is 43994.71 hac which indicates the increasing urban trends in the region. Waterbodies just increased up-to 50.41 hac with during the study period indicating a stable water way through the region.

4.2. ESVs

Ecosystem services values increased by 247.52 million USD during the span of 23 years from year 2000 to 2023. The major increment is observed in ES sub-type recreation which is 58.90% from 696.96 million USD (22.80%) to 1107.50 million USD (33.52%) of total ESVs. This huge increase has happened due to urbanization of the region because where there is urbanization, parks will be built for recreational and entertainment purposes. The second most increasing ecosystem service is climate regulation which has been increased by 30.77% from 218.95 million USD to 286.33 million USD. According to (Costanza *et al.*, 1997) climate regulation controls both local and global processes pertaining to temperature regulation, precipitation, air quality, greenhouse effect, ozone layer, and atmospheric chemical composition. The main factor responsible for the rise in ESVs of climate regulation is the increase in cropland area which provide all the services related to climate regulation. Other ecosystem services which have been increased are soil formation, water regulation and water supply with the increase of 4.67%, 0.91% and 0.67% of total ESVs, respectively.

Significant reduction is observed in Cultural, Habitat/refugia and Gas regulation with the decline of 56.32% in all. The only factor effecting this decline is the area of natural vegetation. We have observed the significant decline in the area of natural vegetation which provides gas regulation, habitat to animals and insect species and responsible for cultural attributes.

Conclusion

In this study we examined the change in LULCs in Sargodha district and how they are impacting the ecosystem services. We analyzed that the significant increase in cropland and built-up area and the conversion of natural vegetation to cropland and built-up area specifies the region's focus on agriculture and urbanization trends. Net ESVs are increasing just because of the increase in cropland area but on the other side, reduction in the area of natural vegetation is also significantly affecting most of the important ecosystem services including aesthetic values, raw materials production and habitat for animal species. Policies for decision-making are necessary to guarantee the sustainability of ESs, particularly those drivers that have a negative effect on the ecosystem. By assessing the ESV at a specific temporal scale and projecting the change over time, errors and uncertainties can be reduced or balanced. For this reason, the Sargodha case study offers enough details about the assessment of LULCs and their effects on the ESVs.

Declaration of conflicting interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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